

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

**Supplementary Information for
“Probabilistic description of protein backbone
motions and conformations”**

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Table of contents

Supplementary information chapter 3	I
Supplementary information chapter 4	19
Supplementary information chapter 6	23

Supplementary information chapter 3

Supplementary Fig. 3.1: **Cross-validation of probability density kernels of conformational states.** The kernels were fitted five times, leaving out 20% of the ensembles each time. The plots show the correlation between probability densities sampled from the five different kernels.

Supplementary Fig. 3.2: **Influence of the sample size on the conformational state variability.** Conformational state variabilities were calculated for all residues in the MD ensembles employing bootstrapping with different sample sizes (10,000 samples). The resulting values were plotted in ascending order (blue), while the dashed line (orange) represents an ideal line between the minimum and maximum values. Thus, the area between the two lines is a measure of the linearity of the conformational state variability in the dataset. As the sample size increases, less samples fall in the linear section of the conformational state variability metric. A sample size of 3 was chosen to obtain informative conformational state variabilities from ensembles for presenting the highest linearity in the metric while also spanning over a decent value range (min-max, see Supplementary Fig. 3.3).

Supplementary Fig. 3.3: **Range of conformational state variability values as a function of the sample size.** Conformational state variabilities were calculated for all residues in the MD ensembles employing bootstrapping with different sample sizes (10,000 samples). The minimum and maximum values are shown here. Initially, as the sample size increases, the range between minimum and maximum values increases as well, reaching a maximum at a sample size of 15. For low sample sizes, conformational state variabilities of 0 are practically not observed. This indicates that even smallest fluctuations of the backbone dihedrals lead to an increase in conformational state variability. As the sample size increase, those small fluctuations become less important, allowing for conformational state variabilities that are practically 0.

Supplementary Fig. 3.4: **Analysis of sampling parameters for molecular dynamics simulations.** Five proteins were simulated to assess the impact of different sampling parameters on the results. From all simulations the conformational state variabilities were calculated using the sliding window-approach with a window size of 3. Results are shown as the conformational state variability along the sequence for different sampling parameters. a) Analysis of the of the impact of simulation time. Results after 100 ns did not differ much from longer simulations. b) Analysis of the impact of sampling intervals. Only minor changes were observed. Sampling in intervals of 1,000 ps was chosen for the final simulations in this work, to minimize the autocorrelation between subsequent sampling time points.

Supplementary Fig. 3.5: **Comparison of conformational diversity between MD ensembles and CoDNaS.** For a given protein the maximum RMSD values between any structures in CoDNaS (x-axis) and the MD ensemble (y-axis) are depicted. With two exceptions (1mjc and 1xq8) the MD simulations produced more diverse ensembles than the structures in CoDNaS. For some structures (e.g., 1z2m and 1bq0) the conformational variability in the simulation strongly exceeded that in CoDNaS. This is mostly due to flexible termini, which MD simulations sample freely. A notable exception is 1rk9, which remains fully folded throughout the simulation but undergoes a conformational change which results in a higher RMSD than observed in CoDNaS. Out of the 113 simulated proteins, only 22 are annotated in CoDNaS.

PDB: 2rr6

Supplementary Fig. 3.6: **Impact of the sample size on conformational states probabilities in human acidic leucine-rich nuclear phosphoprotein 32 family member B (PDB ID: 2rr6).** Conformational state propensities were inferred from the MD ensembles employing bootstrapping with sample sizes 3 and 25 (10,000 samples). As the sample size increases, ambiguous assignments (shades of orange) become less apparent, rather a preferred conformational state is assigned with high propensity (shades of red). On the first two rows, the low probability for Surrounding sheet in the circled area disappears in favour of higher probabilities towards Core sheet. Similarly, in the last two rows the green circled region experiences an increase in Core helix probability. Contrarily, the purple circled region experiences an increase Surrounding helix probability in detriment of Core helix probability.

Supplementary Fig. 3.7: **Relation between Constava conformational states and DSSP secondary structure assignments.** Constava conformational state propensities were correlated with DSSP propensities (average fraction of frames assigned to a given secondary structure by DSSP). The two classification schemes were compared in bins. The bar plot below the correlation plots shows the number of samples (residues) in each bin. a) For Core helix propensities there is a correlation to H (α -helix). b) For Surrounding helix propensities no clear correlations to any DSSP category can be observed. The values for bins with propensities > 0.8 cannot be properly interpreted due to the low number of samples. c) For Core sheet there is a correlation with E (β -sheet). d) For Surrounding sheet no clear correlations are apparent. There is some correlation with E, but the relationship is non-linear and the low number of samples for propensities > 0.6 makes the interpretation difficult. e) For Turn a correlation with T (hydrogen bonded turns) emerges but other DSSP categories are observed for all levels of Turn propensity. f) Finally, the Other propensity mostly associates to C (coil), but also other DSSP categories are observed for all levels of Other propensity. Since Turn and Other indicate highly dynamic residues, it makes sense, that these residues form other secondary structure elements transiently.

Supplementary Fig. 3.8: **Relation between Constava conformational states and STRIDE secondary structure assignments.** Constava conformational state propensities were correlated with STRIDE propensities (average fraction of frames assigned to a given secondary structure by STRIDE). The two classification schemes were compared in bins. The bar plot below the correlation plots shows the number of samples (residues) in each bin. a) For Core helix propensities there is a correlation to H (α -helix). b) For Surrounding helix propensities no clear correlations to any STRIDE category can be observed. The values for bins with propensities > 0.8 cannot be properly interpreted due to the low number of samples. c) For Core sheet there is a correlation with E (β -sheet). d) For Surrounding sheet no clear correlations are apparent. There is some correlation with E, but the relationship is non-linear and the low number of samples for propensities > 0.6 makes the interpretation difficult. e) For Turn a correlation with T (hydrogen bonded turns) emerges but other STRIDE categories are observed for all levels of Turn propensity. f) Finally, the Other propensity mostly associates to C (coil), but also other STRIDE categories are observed for all levels of Other propensity. Since Turn and Other indicate highly dynamic residues, it makes sense, that these residues form other secondary structure elements transiently.

Supplementary Fig. 3.9: **Comparison of Constava and traditional secondary structure assignments with respect to their ability to detect transiently forming secondary structure elements.**

Supplementary Fig. 3.9: (Continuation) Constava, DSSP, and STRIDE were applied to all conformations in the MD trajectories. Shown are: a) Core helix propensities, b) DSSP H (α -helix) assignments, and c) STRIDE H (α -helix) assignments along the MD trajectory of Endonuclease V (PDB ID: 2end). Beyond the relation between propensities and fractions in Supplementary Fig. 7 and Supplementary Fig. 8, Constava shows the capability to detect conformational states before the criteria for the other methods are met. In addition to returning high Core helix probability to the stable helix regions that DSSP and STRIDE assign, some regions with more dynamic behaviour interestingly show detection of helix propensity. The region between amino acids 95-101 is detected to have notable Core helix propensity (a) by Constava throughout the totality of the simulation, even though it is rarely assigned by DSSP (b) and STRIDE (c) in the MD time steps. Additionally, the region between amino acids 39-45 shows a similar tendency, with a longer amino acid range of high Core helix propensities near in the 300 ns time step, where DSSP and STRIDE detect α -helix. This longer stretch indicates that enough amino acids to form the necessary hydrogen bonds for DSSP and STRIDE assignment have adopted Core helix conformation. Finally, the region between amino acids 55-60 is also detected along the whole simulation, while DSSP and STRIDE intermittently assigns α -helix.

Supplementary Fig. 3.10: Comparison of conformational state variability with traditional dynamics metrics per prevalent conformational state.

Supplementary Fig. 3.10: (Continuation) Conformational state propensities were inferred from the MD ensembles employing bootstrapping with sample sizes 3 (10,000 samples). The results were subdivided by their prevalent conformational state. From top to bottom these are: Core helix, Surrounding helix, Core sheet, Surrounding sheet, Turn and Other. In the left column, the conformational state variability is potted against the root mean square fluctuations (RMSF). In the central column, the conformational state variability is plotted against the circular variance. On the right, the conformational state variability is plotted against the S_{RCI}^2 . The vertical dotted lines indicate the border between likely disordered, context-dependent and ordered residues (left to right) as defined in previous work [1]. The horizontal dotted line is a visual guide to distinguish between residues with very low and higher conformational state variability.

Supplementary Fig. 3.II: **Conformational state variability values per amino acid type according to their order preference, terminal regions included.** Conformational state variabilities were calculated for all residues in the MD ensembles employing bootstrapping with sample size 3 (10,000 samples). Amino acids were classified depending on their intrinsic order preference according to the classification on previous work₁ as preferentially ordered (cysteine, phenylalanine, isoleucine, leucine, valine, tryptophan & tyrosine), neutral (alanine, glutamic acid, lysine, methionine, glutamine, arginine, threonine & histidine) and preferentially disordered (aspartic acid, glycine, asparagine, proline & serine). Amino acids which prefer order generally featured lower conformational state variability values than the remaining. The homologous figure with terminal residues removed can be found in the main text, Figure 5. This figure mainly differs in the variability values distribution for methionine, which features higher values in this figure than in Figure 6. This is due to the preferential location of Methionine at the N-terminal region of the protein, which is less bound to inter-residue interactions and allows for easier conformational state changes and therefore variability.

Supplementary Fig. 3.12: **Schematic representation of the conformational states as energy landscapes.** a) Cross section through the energy landscapes along the line of projection (shown in panel b). coreHelix and coreSheet conformational states are defined by a single deep energy well, vastly restricting backbone mobility. The states surrHelix and surrSheet show lowered energy barriers, allowing for more backbone mobility. Finally, in the Other and Turn conformational states, most of the dihedral space is accessible with only minor energy barriers in between. b) Schematic overview of the definition of the conformational states, as well as the line of projection used in panel a.

Supplementary Fig. 3.13: **Conformational states propensities vs conformational state variability.** The metrics were calculated using bootstrapping with a sample size of 3 (10,000 samples). Conformational state propensities for each conformational state are plotted on the x axes, while the y axes show the conformational state variability. As the conformational state propensity for a single conformational state approaches 1, the conformational state variability drops to 0. In contrast, no such correlation can be observed in the left half of the plots. As the probability for a given conformational state approaches 0, the residue may still assume any of the remaining five states, and transition between them, thus, allowing for no conclusions on the conformational state variability.

Supplementary Fig. 3.14: **Entropy of the conformational states in the (ϕ, ψ) -space.** The entropy is a measure of how sensitive the conformational states are to minor changes in the backbone dihedrals in the corresponding areas. The area around $(0, 0)$ is not populated in any of the conformational state models. Thus, the entropy in this region approaches 0.

Supplementary Fig. 3.15: **Co-occurrence of conformational states.** a) This plot shows the overall co-occurrence of conformational states in individual residues. For every residue with a given most likely conformational state (vertical axis), the average remaining propensities for all other states are shown (horizontal axis). b) This plot shows the probabilities of residues transitioning between conformational states between two subsequent time points. Both plots were obtained with window size 3. The labels correspond to the conformational states as follows: cH (Core helix), sH (Surrounding helix), T (Turn), O (Other), sE (Surrounding sheet), cE (Core sheet).

Supplementary Data 3.1 List of proteins according to order class.

Disordered: 2aqc, 1xq8, 1mjc, 1u96, 1ss3, 2kbz, 2l95, 1nq4, 1vdo, 1y00, 1rk9, 2l50, 1yob, 1rqs, 1czh.

Half-disordered: 2jo6, 2rvh, 2khz, 1akp, 2m2u, 2ho9, 2m9v, 2joy, 2mlw, 2lnu, 1b75, 2ot2, 1c9h, 2l7w, 1rit, 2l49, 2l9n, 2myi, 2ls7, 1o13, 2lvh, 2l60, 5vo7, 2kly, 2l25, 1wm2, 2kpq, 2kg7, 1l7y, 2gqb, 1eni, 1zzm, 2den, 2jra, 2jyz, 2jz4, 2moy, 2m2a, 2mc9, 2mhe, 2mvz, 2x8n, 4beh, 4eyv, 5jtk.

Structured: 2mkx, 1jqr, 2fm4, 1jw3, 2rr6, 1hg7, 1spo, 2kva, 3hnx, 1tm9, 1om2, 2d49, 2hfi, 1ufn, 1qkh, 2fvt, 1rzs, 1x3a, 1ey1, 1wjt, 2hgk, 2k2t, 2jny, 2jso, 2rn4, 1bqo, 1g9l, 1imq, 1iyr, 1jh3, 1jw2, 1mpi, 1nnv, 1nzp, 1rq6, 1rrz, 1ryk, 1tog, 1tl6, 1v66, 1v9v, 1xhs, 2ebm, 2end, 2gbs, 2hfq, 2jgx, 2jov, 2jrr, 2jv2, 2jzv, 2ken, 2lfj.

Supplementary Data 3.2 List of proteins mapped to NMR metrics. Only the following subset of MD proteins had their corresponding Random Coil Index information available:

2m2a, 1jw2, 2ls7, 1tog, 2jny, 1tm9, 1v66, 2gqb, 2ebm, 2kpq, 1ryk, 2gbs, 2fvt, 2ken, 1b75, 2l25, 2rr6, 1iyr, 2hfi, 2ho9, 1akp, 2fm4, 1xhs, 1l7y, 1ufn, 2mlw, 1ey1, 2kva, 2mvz, 2lnu, 2lfj, 1om2, 2jyz, 2mhe, 1v9v, 2l49, 1jqr, 1x3a, 1g9l, 2rvh, 5vo7, 1bqo, 2l60, 1c9h, 2jov, 2ot2, 2joy, 2rn4, 2hgk, 1jh3, 2jz4, 5jtk, 1rzs, 2jso, 2kbz, 1rq6, 2jzv, 1wjt, 1jw3, 2jrr, 1hg7, 1imq.

Supplementary information chapter 4

Supplementary Table 4.1: **Tools description.** Simple description of every tool contained in bio2Byte tools.

Predictor	Usage
DynaMine	Fast predictor of protein backbone dynamics using only sequence information as input. The current version also predicts side-chain dynamics and secondary structure predictors using the same principle.
DisoMine	Predicts protein disorder with recurrent neural networks not directly from the amino acid sequence, but instead from more generic predictions of key biophysical properties, here protein dynamics, secondary structure and early folding.
EfoldMine	Predicts from the primary amino acid sequence of a protein, which amino acids are likely involved in early folding events.
AgMata	Single-sequence based predictor of protein regions that are likely to cause beta-aggregation.
PSPer	PSP (Phase Separating Protein) predicts whether a protein is likely to phase-separate with a particular mechanism involving RNA interacts (FUS-like proteins). It will highlight protein regions that are involved mechanistically, and provide an overall score.
ShiftCrypt	Auto-encoding NMR chemical shifts from their native vector space to a residue-level biophysical index.

Supplementary Table 4.2: **Overview of internal tool dependencies.** The predictors contained in this software suite often require the execution of other predictors in our suite. The optimisation process is explained in the main text and the list of dependencies is described in this table.

Tool	Dependencies
DynaMine	None
EFoldMine	DynaMine
DisoMine	DynaMine, EFoldMine
AGmata	DynaMine, EFoldMine
PSPer	DynaMine, EFoldMine, DisoMine
ShiftCrypt	None

Supplementary Table 4.3: **Python Versions and Distribution Sources for all the manually generated Docker images.** For each new release of bio2Byte Tools, the following set of Docker images are generated and published on <https://hub.docker.com/r/bio2byte/b2btools> for additional control over the version of Python and the provenance of the dependencies.

Python Version	Source	Description
3.7	PyPI	Generated from PyPI distributions using Python 3.7.
3.7	Conda	Generated from Conda distributions using Python 3.7.
3.7	System	Generated from System packages using Python 3.7.
3.8	PyPI	Generated from PyPI distributions using Python 3.8.
3.8	Conda	Generated from Conda distributions using Python 3.8.
3.8	System	Generated from System packages using Python 3.8.
3.9	PyPI	Generated from PyPI distributions using Python 3.9.
3.9	Conda	Generated from Conda distributions using Python 3.9.
3.9	System	Generated from System packages using Python 3.9.
3.10	PyPI	Generated from PyPI distributions using Python 3.10.
3.10	Conda	Generated from Conda distributions using Python 3.10.
3.10	System	Generated from System packages using Python 3.10.
3.11	PyPI	Generated from PyPI distributions using Python 3.11.
3.11	Conda	Generated from Conda distributions using Python 3.11.
3.11	System	Generated from System packages using Python 3.11.
3.12	PyPI	Generated from PyPI distributions using Python 3.12.
3.12	Conda	Generated from Conda distributions using Python 3.12.
3.12	System	Generated from System packages using Python 3.12.

Supplementary Fig. 4.1: **Pytest process diagram.** The package testing process starts from a single Git repository, which then creates an environment per Python version from 3.7 to 3.12. For each environment, a series of tests on the source code are executed, namely the execution of single sequence, multiple sequence, parsers, and ShiftCrypt/NMR modules. Then the outputs get compared to ground results values and assessed for differences beyond float point errors (sum of absolute differences across all predicted metrics and residues, proteins and residues smaller than 0.001). A python package is then created and single sequence and multiple sequence modules are newly tested. If all tests across all Python versions are satisfactory, the python package will be uploaded to PyPI and to Bioconda. Then, an array of Docker images are created and uploaded to Docker Hub, following the settings in Supplementary Table 4.3. Finally, Bioconda automatically deposits a docker container with the Python 3.10 version of the package in Biocontainers, which can then be deployed into Galaxy.

Supplementary information chapter 6: NMR-derived

Supplementary Fig. 6.1: **pLDDT values per amino acid order classes.** The amino acids from the S_{RCI}^2 dataset were clustered in 3 classes according to their order preference: preferentially ordered (cysteine, phenylalanine, isoleucine, leucine, valine, tryptophan & tyrosine; $N=106,363$), neutral (alanine, glutamic acid, lysine, methionine, glutamine, arginine, threonine & histidine; $N=155,050$) and preferentially disordered (aspartic acid, glycine, asparagine, proline & serine; $N=112,945$). The distributions were tested with a Mann–Whitney U test, which resulted in p-values < 0.001 in all tests.

Supplementary Fig. 6.2: **Abundance of secondary structures by pLDDT ranges.** A) The STRIDE secondary structure assignment from the structure that AlphaFold2 produces. B) The STRIDE consensus secondary structure assignment here provided is the most abundantly assigned secondary structure in the ensemble of NMR structures available. The STRIDE consensus assignment (panel B) produces a decrease in abundance for helix (H) and sheet (E) fractions as the pLDDT decreases, as well as an increase in coil (C) and turn (T) conformations. These tendencies are maintained for AlphaFold2's single structure assignment (panel A) in sheet and coil fractions, but not for helix and turn.

Supplementary Fig. 6.3: Comparison of pLDDT and δ^2D populations. Caption in next page.

Supplementary Fig. 6.3: (Continuation) For all available residues in the S_{RCI}^2 dataset, the populations of conformational states were calculated with $\delta 2D$ method. High populations values of a conformation indicate high presence of such conformation in the ensemble, and vice-versa. A-D: For both Helix and Sheet conformations, higher $\delta 2D$ populations are obtained for residues featuring high pLDDT (≥ 80 , $N=62,014$), gradually adopting lower populations for mid ($80 > \text{pLDDT} \geq 60$, $N=8,539$) and low (< 60 , $N=4,773$) pLDDT values. E-H: Coil and PPII populations are prominently higher for higher for low pLDDT ranges than for mid and high ranges. Mann-Whitney two-sided U tests p-values between each pLDDT-stratified distribution for each $\delta 2D$ conformation confirmed difference at p-values < 0.001 (Supplementary Table 6.2).

Supplementary Fig. 6.4: **Comparison between AlphaFoldz pLDDT and Constava's conformational state propensities.** Caption in next page.

Supplementary Fig. 6.4: (Continuation) The pLDDT of each residue was plotted against the propensity for each of the 6 conformational states calculated in Constava. Any propensity below 0.05 was deemed non-informative and discarded to facilitate interpretation. All residues in the MD dataset were stratified in high (N=9,523), mid (N=1,038) and low (N=809) AlphaFold2 ranges. A & B) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Core Helix propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. C & D) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Surrounding Helix propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. E & F) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Core Sheet propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. G & H) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Surrounding Sheet propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. I & J) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Turn propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. K & L) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Other propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. The p-values for the Mann-Whitney two-sided U tests between each pLDDT-stratified distribution for every conformational state can be found in Supplementary Table 6.1.

Supplementary Fig. 6.5: **Comparison of pLDDT and solvent accessibility.** A) The AlphaFold2 pLDDT in the S_{RCI}^2 dataset were plotted against the solvent accessibility score for every residue with available values, in an hexagonal binning plot. B) Distributions of solvent accessibility scores, stratified in high (≥ 80 , $N=62,319$), mid ($80 > \text{pLDDT} \geq 60$, $N=8,708$) and low (< 60 , $N=4,842$) AlphaFold2 pLDDT values. Mann-Whitney two-sided U test confirmed significant differences between all distribution pairs with a p-value < 0.001 (Supplementary Table 6.3).

Supplementary Fig. 6.6: **AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs. conformational state variability.** A) High pLDDT values (≥ 80 , $N = 10,272$) concentrate in areas with lower conformational state variability. Low pLDDT (< 60 , $N = 463$) usually correspond to residues with high conformational state variability. B) This tendency is more clearly observed with pLDDT-stratified distributions, which shows that low pLDDT residues correspond to residues with high conformational state variability, therefore with high potential to exist in multiple conformations, and vice-versa for high pLDDT and low variability residues. Mid pLDDT residues ($80 > \text{pLDDT} \geq 60$, $N = 634$) exhibit an intermediate distribution. Mann-Whitney two-sided U test yielded a p-value < 0.001 between all distributions (Supplementary Table 6.3). The associated distributions per propensity can be found in Supplementary Fig. 6.7.

Supplementary Fig. 6.7: **Comparison between AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT and Constava's conformational state propensities.** Caption in next page.

Supplementary Fig. 6.7: (Continuation) The pLDDT of each residue was plotted against the propensity for each of the 6 conformational states calculated in Constava. Any propensity below 0.05 was deemed non-informative and discarded to facilitate interpretation. All residues in the MD dataset were stratified in high (N=10,272), mid (N=634) and low (N=463) AlphaFold3 C- α ranges. A & B) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Core Helix propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. C & D) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Surrounding Helix propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. E & F) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Core Sheet propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. G & H) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Surrounding Sheet propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. I & J) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Turn propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. K & L) Hexagonal binning of AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT vs Other propensity and its associated pLDDT-stratified distributions. The p-values for the Mann-Whitney two-sided U tests between each pLDDT-stratified distribution for every conformational state can be found in Supplementary Table 6.1.

Supplementary Fig. 6.8: **Comparison between AlphaFold3 C- α pLDDT and S^2 .** Most residues in this dataset exhibit high pLDDT and high S^2 values, represented by warmer hues in panel A. Due to the limited and uneven residues sample sizes (high pLDDT, ≥ 80 , N = 4,125; mid pLDDT, $80 > \text{pLDDT} \geq 60$, N = 287; low pLDDT, < 60 , N = 70), it is challenging to make definitive conclusions about the sparsely populated mid and low pLDDT regions. Panel B illustrates the distributions of S^2 values of each pLDDT range, for which Mann-Whitney two-sided U test yielded a p-value < 0.001 between all distributions (Supplementary Table 6.3).

Supplementary Fig. 6.9: **Distribution of STRIDE fold assignment matches and mismatches between AlphaFold2 structures and consensus NMR ensemble assignments, for diverse metrics.** Those residues in the S^2_{RCI} dataset with STRIDE consensus were stratified according to their secondary assignment pairs, derived from AlphaFold2 structures and the NMR models consensus assignment. A, D & G) pLDDT distributions for residues whose consensus STRIDE assignment from NMR ensembles and from AlphaFold2 models match or mismatch. B, E & H) S^2_{RCI} distributions for residues whose consensus STRIDE assignment from NMR ensembles and from AlphaFold2 models match or mismatch. C, F & I) shiftCrypt distributions for residues whose consensus STRIDE assignment from NMR ensembles and from AlphaFold2 models match or mismatch.

Supplementary Fig. 6.10: **Distribution of residues with NMR consensus STRIDE assignment with and without unique STRIDE assignment, for diverse metrics.** Those residues in the S^2_{RCI} dataset with STRIDE consensus were stratified according to whether they featured a unique STRIDE assignment across all the models in their corresponding NMR ensemble. A, D, G & J) pLDDT distributions for α -helix, coil, turn and β -sheet respectively. B, E, H & K) S^2_{RCI} distributions for α -helix, coil, turn and β -sheet respectively. C, F, I & L) shiftCrpt distributions for α -helix, coil, turn and β -sheet respectively.

Supplementary Fig. 6.II: **Distribution of residues with NMR consensus STRIDE assignment with and without unique STRIDE assignment, with matching and mismatching NMR and AlphaFold2 fold assignments, for diverse metrics.** Those residues in the S^2_{RCI} dataset with STRIDE consensus were stratified according to whether they featured a unique STRIDE assignment across all the models in their corresponding NMR ensemble. Then, they were further stratified on whether or not their NMR consensus STRIDE assignment matched the AlphaFold2 STRIDE assignment. A, D, G & J) pLDDT distributions for α -helix, coil, turn and β -sheet respectively. B, E, H & K) S^2_{RCI} distributions for α -helix, coil, turn and β -sheet respectively. C, F, I & L) shiftCrupt distributions for α -helix, coil, turn and β -sheet respectively.

Supplementary Table 6.I: **Results of the Mann-Whitney two-sided U tests between pLDDT-stratified subsets per Constava's conformational states on the MD dataset.** For each of Constava's conformational states, the pLDDT-stratified subsets were tested against each other with a Mann-Whitney two-sided U test to assess differential distributions.

Conformational state	AlphaFold version	pLDDT ranges	Difference between means	p-value
Core Helix	2	High-Mid	0.2161	6.67×10^{-34}
Core Helix	2	High-Low	0.3427	2.52×10^{-31}
Core Helix	2	Mid-Low	0.1266	1.53×10^{-5}
Surr. Helix	2	High-Mid	0.0264	0.01955
Surr. Helix	2	High-Low	0.1168	5.17×10^{-43}
Surr. Helix	2	Mid-Low	0.0903	1.24×10^{-20}
Core Sheet	2	High-Mid	0.2254	1.60×10^{-60}
Core Sheet	2	High-Low	0.3074	2.12×10^{-104}
Core Sheet	2	Mid-Low	0.0821	1.58×10^{-5}
Surr. Sheet	2	High-Mid	0.0339	1.96×10^{-8}
Surr. Sheet	2	High-Low	0.0455	3.02×10^{-15}
Surr. Sheet	2	Mid-Low	0.0117	0.08711
Turn	2	High-Mid	0.0394	0.44796
Turn	2	High-Low	0.0826	0.22141
Turn	2	Mid-Low	0.0432	0.45743
Other	2	High-Mid	0.0082	0.28323
Other	2	High-Low	-0.0397	6.19×10^{-15}
Other	2	Mid-Low	-0.0479	1.85×10^{-9}
Core Helix	3	High-Mid	0.1990	4.07×10^{-14}
Core Helix	3	High-Low	0.3498	4.63×10^{-20}
Core Helix	3	Mid-Low	0.1507	1.85×10^{-4}
Surr. Helix	3	High-Mid	0.0861	6.18×10^{-18}
Surr. Helix	3	High-Low	0.1203	7.55×10^{-27}
Surr. Helix	3	Mid-Low	0.0343	0.00256
Core Sheet	3	High-Mid	0.2657	1.94×10^{-58}
Core Sheet	3	High-Low	0.3019	6.68×10^{-64}
Core Sheet	3	Mid-Low	0.0362	0.29869
Surr. Sheet	3	High-Mid	0.0423	6.90×10^{-10}
Surr. Sheet	3	High-Low	0.0462	1.51×10^{-10}
Surr. Sheet	3	Mid-Low	0.0039	0.66095
Turn	3	High-Mid	0.0628	0.48281
Turn	3	High-Low	0.0779	0.13434
Turn	3	Mid-Low	0.0152	0.33197
Other	3	High-Mid	-0.0178	0.000078
Other	3	High-Low	-0.0288	2.72×10^{-8}
Other	3	Mid-Low	-0.0110	0.15908

Supplementary Table 6.2: **Results of the Mann-Whitney two-sided U tests between pLDDT-stratified subsets for S_{RCI}^2 $\delta 2D$ conformations in AlphaFold2.** For each conformation type, the pLDDT-stratified subsets were tested against each other with a Mann-Whitney two-sided U test to assess differential distributions. *Note: p-values marked with * were too low for Scipy to differentiate from 0.*

Conformation	pLDDT ranges	Difference between means	p-value
$\delta 2D$ Helix	High-Mid	0.1185	3.38×10^{-55}
$\delta 2D$ Helix	High-Low	0.2896	0.0*
$\delta 2D$ Helix	Mid-Low	0.1711	1.23×10^{-300}
$\delta 2D$ Sheet	High-Mid	0.1181	5.03×10^{-49}
$\delta 2D$ Sheet	High-Low	0.1723	5.44×10^{-53}
$\delta 2D$ Sheet	Mid-Low	0.0542	2.63×10^{-7}
$\delta 2D$ Coil	High-Mid	-0.1775	0.0*
$\delta 2D$ Coil	High-Low	-0.3184	0.0*
$\delta 2D$ Coil	Mid-Low	-0.1410	3.76×10^{-305}
$\delta 2D$ PPII	High-Mid	-0.0592	0.0*
$\delta 2D$ PPII	High-Low	-0.1435	0.0*
$\delta 2D$ PPII	Mid-Low	-0.0843	0.0*

Supplementary Table 6.3: **Results of the Mann-Whitney two-sided U tests between pLDDT-stratified subsets.** For each dataset, the pLDDT-stratified subsets were tested against each other with a Mann-Whitney two-sided U test to assess differential distributions. *Note: p-values marked with * were too low for Scipy to differentiate from 0.*

Dataset	Metric	AlphaFold version	pLDDT ranges	Difference between means	p-value
S_{RCI}^2	S_{RCI}^2	2	high-mid	0.1417	0*
S_{RCI}^2	S_{RCI}^2	2	high-low	0.4150	0*
S_{RCI}^2	S_{RCI}^2	2	mid-low	0.2732	0*
S_{RCI}^2	ShiftCrypt	2	high-mid	0.0152	0.002
S_{RCI}^2	ShiftCrypt	2	high-low	-0.0201	4.55×10^{-7}
S_{RCI}^2	ShiftCrypt	2	mid-low	-0.0353	9.45×10^{-21}
S_{RCI}^2	Solvent accessibility	2	high-mid	-0.1851	0*
S_{RCI}^2	Solvent accessibility	2	high-low	-0.3521	0*
S_{RCI}^2	Solvent accessibility	2	mid-low	-0.1670	1.93×10^{-297}
S^2	S^2	2	high-mid	0.1352	5.60×10^{-24}
S^2	S^2	2	high-low	0.4238	1.19×10^{-53}
S^2	S^2	2	mid-low	0.2886	2.12×10^{-19}
S^2	S^2	3	high-mid	0.1681	1.74×10^{-43}
S^2	S^2	3	high-low	0.4904	6.36×10^{-38}
S^2	S^2	3	mid-low	0.3223	2.45×10^{-16}
MD	Conf. state var.	2	high-mid	-0.1468	3.46×10^{-143}
MD	Conf. state var.	2	high-low	-0.2197	1.23×10^{-246}
MD	Conf. state var.	2	mid-low	-0.0729	1.48×10^{-22}
MD	Conf. state var.	3	high-mid	-0.1743	1.46×10^{-126}
MD	Conf. state var.	3	high-low	-0.2258	4.6×10^{-155}
MD	Conf. state var.	3	mid-low	-0.0515	2.08×10^{-7}

Supplementary information chapter 6: NMA-derived

On the S_{RCI}^2 dataset of 762 proteins, WEBnma was carried out on the 762 AlphaFold2 models. Therefore, based on WEBnma output, the final dataset consists of 762 AlphaFold2 models. The predicted RMSF values of each coil residue in all 762 proteins are shown in (Supplementary Fig. 6.12). The supplementary figure shows some extreme RMSF values in low-pLDDT regions. As explained in the main text, these extreme values can originate artificially from loosely packed stretches in the protein structure. We have therefore adapted the RMSF analysis to reduce the artificial RMSF outliers. As shown in the following (section Truncation criterion), the N- and C-terminal tails from AlphaFold2 models were truncated. The truncation criterion is based on the number of $C\alpha$ contacts. The final number of truncated proteins in the dataset was 755, and the remaining 7 did not require cutting of termini. Subsequently, normal mode analysis with WEBnma was again performed on these 755 truncated models, and the RMSF was recomputed. The RMSF results are shown for 762 proteins, including both the 755 truncated models and the 7 models that did not require termini cutting (referred to as truncated S_{RCI}^2 dataset). Apart from (Supplementary Fig. 6.12, Supplementary Fig. 6.13, and Supplementary Table 6.4) all figures and data in the main document and SI contain the RMSF of truncated S_{RCI}^2 dataset. Supplementary Fig. 6.13 shows the effect of the truncation by comparing the RMSF before truncation and the RMSF after truncation.

Supplementary Fig. 6.12: **Comparison of pLDDT and RMSF in coils.** pLDDT vs RMSF of 762 proteins for coil residues before truncation. The colour bar represents the Gaussian kernel density estimate of the dataset. The red vertical lines divide the dataset into high pLDDT (≥ 80), mid ($60 \leq \text{pLDDT} < 80$) and low (< 60) pLDDT regions.

Supplementary Fig. 6.13: **Comparison of pLDDT and RMSF in coils.** RMSF vs pLDDT of amino acid residues exhibiting coils in non-truncated (A, C, E) and truncated (B, D, F) AlphaFold2 structures in low-pLDDT (A, B), mid-pLDDT (C, D), and c) high-pLDDT (E, F) regions. Only the amino acids that are present in both the non-truncated and truncated AlphaFold2 models are included.

Supplementary Table 6.4: **RMSF values of are grouped according to pLDDT in low-pLDDT, mid-pLDDT and high-pLDDT for AlphaFold2 models before truncation.** The table reports the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation for each group.

Secondary structure	pLDDT range	min	max	mean	std
Coil	low	0.22	184.99	6.28	5.83
Strand	low	0.28	8.05	1.81	1.66
α -helix	low	0.24	25.98	2.11	2.15
Turn	low	0.22	37.15	2.62	2.74
3_{10} -helix	low	0.29	27.87	2.27	3.29
Bridge	low	0.31	19.52	1.78	2.50
Coil	mid	0.21	112.52	3.00	5.16
Strand	mid	0.23	21.63	1.49	1.60
α -helix	mid	0.18	23.61	2.02	2.37
Turn	mid	0.20	33.05	2.04	2.56
3_{10} -helix	mid	0.21	27.39	2.11	3.07
Bridge	mid	0.26	13.06	1.66	2.04
Coil	high	0.15	33.97	1.58	1.84
Strand	high	0.15	29.67	1.35	1.49
α -helix	high	0.14	24.68	1.57	1.87
Turn	high	0.15	32.52	1.63	1.91
3_{10} -helix	high	0.20	30.04	1.37	1.55
Bridge	high	0.15	29.29	1.48	1.78

Truncation criterion

For determining N- and/or C-termini truncation, the $C\alpha$ contacts were assessed within a 10 Å (1 nm) cut-off for each protein in the dataset. In proteins, helices and strands consistently exhibited significant contacts, surpassing approximately 13 contacts per residue across the dataset with lower RMSF (< 20 Å) as shown in (Supplementary Fig. 6.14). An example is shown in Supplementary Fig. 6.15. In contrast, coils showed fewer than 13 contacts per residue and showed very high RMSF (> 50 Å). Thus, a 13-contact cut-off was selected to truncate the termini. Following this criterion, all first residues with fewer than 13 contacts were cut both in the N-terminal and C-terminal. Consequently, if the first residue of an N- or C-terminal has ≥ 13 contacts, this terminal was not truncated. Only the termini were truncated, so an accidental low contact region in the core of the protein would not get cut.

Supplementary Fig. 6.14: **Mean number of contacts.** Mean number of $C\alpha$ contacts within a 10 Å cut-off for first 30 residues depicting N-terminal (A) and last 30 residues depicting C-terminal (B) averaged over all 762 proteins. The black line represents the mean contacts, with the standard deviation shown as grey shaded area.

Supplementary Fig. 6.15: **Number of $C\alpha$ contacts profile.** (A) and RMSF profile (B) of Q92688. The red dashed line in A represents the contact cut-off (13 contacts) and red dashed line in B represents the RMSF at contact cut-off. The 3D structure of Q92688 is shown in C with a red highlighted region for truncation.

Additional analysis of RMSF and correlation with pLDDT or S_{RCI}^2

The RMSF values for the dataset with truncated dataset are further analysed (now 762 proteins) according to their secondary structure element as predicted by STRIDE.

The six considered secondary structure elements are coil, strand, α -helix, turn, 3_{10} -helix, and bridge. The tables report the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation for the RMSF values in each secondary structure group. Supplementary Table 6.5 gives three columns according to the pLDDT value as given by AlphaFold2: low-pLDDT, mid-pLDDT, and high-pLDDT. Supplementary Table 6.6 gives three columns according to the S_{RCI}^2 value as included in the truncated S_{RCI}^2 dataset: flexible, ambiguous, and rigid.

Next, the Pearson correlation coefficient between the RMSF values and the pLDDT values were computed in each group (low-pLDDT, mid-pLDDT, and high-pLDDT) in (Supplementary Table 6.7). Moreover, the Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and pLDDT was computed, without considering the subgroups of pLDDT (Supplementary Table 6.7). Similarly, the Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S_{RCI}^2 was computed for each group (flexible, ambiguous, and rigid), and without considering subgroups of S_{RCI}^2 (Supplementary Table 6.8). For both RMSF and pLDDT, RMSF and S_{RCI}^2 , the Pearson correlation was calculated for each secondary structure group, and without the classification of secondary structure. Next, the Pearson correlation coefficient between the RMSF values and S_{RCI}^2 can also be computed for each individual AlphaFold2 and NMR model in the truncated S_{RCI}^2 dataset. This is reported as a histogram in Supplementary Fig. 6.18 (blue) using the RMSF values of the 746 AlphaFold2 models and Supplementary Fig. 6.18 (yellow) using the RMSF values of 14,069 NMR models (as explained in the results section 3.5.2).

Supplementary Fig. 6.16: **Comparison of pLDDT and RMSF.** RMSF values versus pLDDT value of each amino acid, visualised with a Gaussian kernel estimator for S_{RCI}^2 data set. One subplot for each secondary structure element: A) coil (N = 105,172), B) strand (N = 54,786), C) α -helix (N = 109,639), D) turn (N = 58,328), E) 3_{10} -helix (N = 7,931), and F) bridge (N = 2,445), where N represents number of amino acid residues. The red vertical lines divide the dataset into high pLDDT (≥ 80), mid ($60 \leq \text{pLDDT} < 80$) and low (< 60) pLDDT regions.

Supplementary Table 6.5: **RMSF values are grouped according to pLDDT in low-pLDDT, mid-pLDDT and high-pLDDT.** The table reports the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation for each group.

Secondary structure	pLDDT range	min	max	mean	std
Coil	low	0.22	49.24	5.65	4.43
Strand	low	0.24	8.82	1.89	1.86
α -Helix	low	0.25	27.35	1.87	1.83
Turn	low	0.20	32.16	2.16	2.03
3_{10} -helix	low	0.25	27.95	2.08	3.19
Bridge	low	0.22	22.78	1.89	3.00
Coil	mid	0.21	26.71	1.89	2.18
Strand	mid	0.21	12.60	1.35	1.46
α -Helix	mid	0.18	27.26	1.84	2.26
Turn	mid	0.15	29.68	1.74	2.16
3_{10} -helix	mid	0.21	32.80	1.89	2.78
Bridge	mid	0.26	13.43	1.34	1.53
Coil	high	0.14	30.48	1.27	1.29
Strand	high	0.14	20.28	1.11	1.13
α -Helix	high	0.13	25.39	1.38	1.65
Turn	high	0.13	20.95	1.33	1.36
3_{10} -helix	high	0.16	17.96	1.14	1.16
Bridge	high	0.15	14.87	1.20	1.16

Supplementary Table 6.6: **RMSF values are grouped according to S_{RCI}^2 values in flexible (< 0.7), ambiguous (0.7-0.8), and rigid(> 0.8).** The table reports the maximum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation for each group.

Secondary structure	S_{RCI}^2	min	max	mean	std
Coil	flexible	0.21	25.06	2.43	2.60
Strand	flexible	0.23	15.44	1.38	1.66
α -Helix	flexible	0.23	20.99	2.04	2.06
Turn	flexible	0.19	22.01	1.89	1.79
3_{10} -helix	flexible	0.23	11.44	1.70	1.94
Bridge	flexible	0.29	9.20	1.52	1.49
Coil	ambiguous	0.20	16.88	1.40	1.58
Strand	ambiguous	0.20	15.16	1.28	1.33
α -Helix	ambiguous	0.21	16.51	1.56	1.72
Turn	ambiguous	0.20	17.37	1.52	1.70
3_{10} -helix	ambiguous	0.21	10.54	1.45	1.45
Bridge	ambiguous	0.22	10.09	1.27	1.34
Coil	rigid	0.19	14.74	1.30	1.47
Strand	rigid	0.17	14.77	1.13	1.25
α -Helix	rigid	0.15	19.04	1.23	1.35
Turn	rigid	0.20	14.70	1.35	1.40
3_{10} -helix	rigid	0.21	11.74	1.21	1.32
Bridge	rigid	0.21	14.87	1.37	1.73

Supplementary Fig. 6.17: **Comparison of S^2_{RCI} and RMSF.** RMSF values versus S^2_{RCI} value of each amino acid, visualised with a Gaussian kernel estimator for truncated S^2_{RCI} data set. One subplot for each secondary structure element: A) coil (N = 11,634), B) strand (N = 18,640), C) α -helix (N = 25,861), D) turn (N = 14,759), E) 3_{10} -helix (N = 2,250), and F) bridge (N = 670), where N represents number of amino acid residues. The green vertical lines divide the dataset into flexible (< 0.70), ambiguous ($0.70 - 0.80$), and rigid (≥ 0.80) regions.

Supplementary Table 6.7: **Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values are provided for RMSF and pLDDT.** These correlations are analysed as well as for the full range of pLDDT, with and without the classification of secondary structure elements (all SS).

Subset	Secondary Structure	Pearson correlation coefficient	p-value
low-pLDDT	Coil	0.16	0.00
mid-pLDDT	Coil	-0.17	8.98×10^{-55}
high-pLDDT	Coil	-0.16	1.90×10^{-157}
all pLDDT	Coil	-0.43	0.00
low-pLDDT	Strand	0.21	4.62×10^{-6}
mid-pLDDT	Strand	-0.01	4.51×10^{-1}
high-pLDDT	Strand	-0.12	8.70×10^{-165}
all pLDDT	Strand	-0.12	1.07×10^{-185}
low-pLDDT	α -helix	0.16	9.41×10^{-36}
mid-pLDDT	α -helix	-0.04	9.19×10^{-7}
high-pLDDT	α -helix	-0.10	1.28×10^{-183}
all pLDDT	α -helix	-0.11	4.49×10^{-319}
low-pLDDT	Turn	0.07	9.71×10^{-15}
mid-pLDDT	Turn	-0.04	1.93×10^{-6}
high-pLDDT	Turn	-0.16	7.83×10^{-208}
all pLDDT	Turn	-0.20	0.00
low-pLDDT	3_{10} -helix	0.13	1.28×10^{-3}
mid-pLDDT	3_{10} -helix	-0.04	1.91×10^{-1}
high-pLDDT	3_{10} -helix	-0.17	3.16×10^{-41}
all pLDDT	3_{10} -helix	-0.19	1.08×10^{-67}
low-pLDDT	Bridge	0.07	4.99×10^{-1}
mid-pLDDT	Bridge	0.00	9.63×10^{-1}
high-pLDDT	Bridge	-0.18	5.08×10^{-17}
all pLDDT	Bridge	-0.14	3.51×10^{-12}
low-pLDDT	All	-0.04	1.93×10^{-26}
mid-pLDDT	All	-0.07	2.99×10^{-47}
high-pLDDT	All	-0.13	0.00
all pLDDT	All	-0.24	0.00

Supplementary Table 6.8: Pearson correlation coefficients and p-values are provided for RMSF and S_{RCI}^2 . These correlations are analysed as well as for the full range of pLDDT, with and without the classification of secondary structure elements (all SS).

Subset	Secondary Structure	Pearson correlation coefficient	p-value
Flexible S_{RCI}^2	Coil	-0.26	3.22×10^{-66}
Ambiguous S_{RCI}^2	Coil	-0.07	7.65×10^{-5}
Rigid S_{RCI}^2	Coil	-0.05	1.27×10^{-3}
All S_{RCI}^2	Coil	-0.32	1.06×10^{-278}
Flexible S_{RCI}^2	Strand	-0.11	4.84×10^{-3}
Ambiguous S_{RCI}^2	Strand	-0.04	2.57×10^{-2}
Rigid S_{RCI}^2	Strand	-0.06	6.85×10^{-15}
All S_{RCI}^2	Strand	-0.08	5.2×10^{-26}
Flexible S_{RCI}^2	α -helix	-0.01	5.62×10^{-1}
Ambiguous S_{RCI}^2	α -helix	-0.08	2.07×10^{-4}
Rigid S_{RCI}^2	α -helix	-0.05	2.66×10^{-14}
All S_{RCI}^2	α -helix	-0.15	4.72×10^{-124}
Flexible S_{RCI}^2	Turn	-0.11	9.50×10^{-13}
Ambiguous S_{RCI}^2	Turn	-0.03	5.21×10^{-2}
Rigid S_{RCI}^2	Turn	-0.03	8.36×10^{-3}
All S_{RCI}^2	Turn	-0.15	1.15×10^{-76}
Flexible S_{RCI}^2	3_{10} -helix	-0.16	1.23×10^{-2}
Ambiguous S_{RCI}^2	3_{10} -helix	-0.02	7.13×10^{-1}
Rigid S_{RCI}^2	3_{10} -helix	-0.08	3.34×10^{-3}
All S_{RCI}^2	3_{10} -helix	-0.14	4.67×10^{-11}
Flexible S_{RCI}^2	Bridge	-0.14	1.34×10^{-1}
Ambiguous S_{RCI}^2	Bridge	-0.18	1.44×10^{-2}
Rigid S_{RCI}^2	Bridge	-0.07	1.91×10^{-1}
All S_{RCI}^2	Bridge	-0.07	6.56×10^{-2}
Flexible S_{RCI}^2	All	-0.17	6.97×10^{-75}
Ambiguous S_{RCI}^2	All	-0.05	4.03×10^{-10}
Rigid S_{RCI}^2	All	-0.06	3.59×10^{-44}
All S_{RCI}^2	All	-0.22	0.00

Supplementary Fig. 6.18: **Pearson correlation coefficients between RMSF and S^2_{RCI} .** Distribution of Pearson correlation coefficients between RMSF values and S^2_{RCI} values of amino acids for AlphaFold2 models (blue) and NMR models (yellow).

Examples of S^2_{RCI} and RMSF correlation for AlphaFold2 and NMR models

The correlation between the per-residue RMSF and per-residue S^2_{RCI} values of a given protein is generally expected to be negative, because rigid regions would correspond to high RMSF and low S^2_{RCI} . There were a few NMR models that showed (unexpected) positive correlation between S^2_{RCI} and RMSF.

Example of a protein where the AlphaFold2 model has a slightly weaker negative S^2_{RCI} versus RMSF correlation than the NMR model

The Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S^2_{RCI} values is -0.52 for the AlphaFold2 model of protein Q96LL9-2YUA (BMRB id III44). For the 20 NMR structures, 19 have a Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S^2_{RCI} that lie in the range -0.65 to -0.81 and the remaining model shows -0.40 . Therefore, the AlphaFold2 model has weaker correlation than

most of the NMR models. In addition, in the figures below, the NMR model shows residues with ambiguous secondary structure (grey). The ambiguous residues were computed by the dumb consensus of secondary structure with a 70% threshold within the NMR ensemble.

Supplementary Fig. 6.19: **Example of a protein (Q96LL9-2YUA)**. The 3D structures with secondary structure mapping colours are shown on the right: AlphaFold2 model (right top) and NMR ensemble (right bottom, 20 NMR models shown at once). Comparing S_{RCI}^2 (red, dashed) and RMSF (black line) of the AlphaFold2 model and the NMR ensemble (for this protein, there were 20 NMR models within the ensemble). The secondary structure is indicated with shaded regions. The pLDDT of the sequence is shown below the plots. (Color legends at the top of the figure.)

Example of a protein where the AlphaFold2 model has a slightly stronger negative S_{RCI}^2 versus RMSF correlation than (most of) the NMR models

The Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S_{RCI}^2 values is -0.91 for the AlphaFold2 model of protein Q922K9-2D8J (BMRB id: 11214). For the 20 NMR models within the ensemble, the Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S_{RCI}^2 lie in the range -0.63 to -0.91 , where 19 models show correlation coefficient below -0.91 . Therefore, the AlphaFold2 model has stronger negative correlation than most of the NMR models.

Supplementary Fig. 6.20: **Example of a protein (Q922K9-2D8J)**. The 3D structures with secondary structure mapping colours are shown on the right: truncated AlphaFold2 model (right top) and NMR ensemble (right bottom, 20 NMR models within the ensemble shown at once). Comparing S^2_{RCI} (red, dashed) and RMSF (black line) of the AlphaFold2 model and the NMR models (for this protein, there were 20). The secondary structure is indicated with shaded regions. The pLDDT of the sequence is shown below the plots.

Example of a protein where the AlphaFold2 model has a (unexpected) positive S^2_{RCI} versus RMSF correlation, while the NMR models show negative correlation

The Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S^2_{RCI} values is 0.63 for the AlphaFold2 model and ranges from -0.62 to -0.85 for the 20 NMR models within the ensemble of protein Q02053-2V31 (BMRB id 18758).

Supplementary Fig. 6.21: **Example of a protein (Q02053-2V31)**. The 3D structures with secondary structure mapping colours are shown on the right: truncated AlphaFold2 model (right top) and NMR ensemble (right bottom, 20 NMR models within the ensemble shown at once). Comparing S^2_{RCI} (red, dashed) and RMSF (black line) of the AlphaFold2 model and the NMR models (for this protein, there were 20). The secondary structure is indicated with shaded regions. The pLDDT of the sequence is shown below the plot.

Example of a protein where the AlphaFold2 model has a negative S^2_{RCI} versus RMSF correlation, while the NMR structure shows (unexpected) positive correlation.

The Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S^2_{RCI} values is -0.40 for the AlphaFold2 model and ranges from 0.00 to 0.09 for the 20 NMR structures of protein P37665-2N48. (BMRB id 15683).

Supplementary Fig. 6.22: **Example of a protein (P₃₇₆₆₅-2N₄₈)**. The 3D structures with secondary structure mapping colours are shown on the right: truncated AlphaFold2 model (right top) and NMR ensemble (right bottom, 20 NMR models within the ensemble shown at once). Comparing S^2_{RCI} (red, dashed) and RMSF (black line) of the AlphaFold2 model and the NMR models (for this protein, there were 20). The secondary structure is indicated with shaded regions. The pLDDT of the sequence is shown below the plots.

Example of a protein where the 88% of overlapping amino acid sequence between AlphaFold2 NMR shows conflicting secondary structure.

The Pearson correlation coefficient between RMSF and S^2_{RCI} values is -0.55 for the AlphaFold2 model and ranges from -0.74 to -0.86 for the 20 NMR structures of protein PoAFWo-2LCL (BMRB id 17615).

Supplementary Fig. 6.23: **Example of a protein (PoAFWo-2LCL)**. The 3D structures with secondary structure mapping colours are shown on the right: AlphaFold2 model overlapping with NMR sequence (right top) and NMR ensemble (right bottom, 20 NMR models within the ensemble shown at once). Comparing S^2_{RCI} (red, dashed) and RMSF (black line) of the truncated AlphaFold2 model and the NMR models (for this protein, there were 20). The secondary structure is indicated with shaded regions. The pLDDT of the sequence is shown below the plot. The sequence in the RMSF plot shows sequence from 101-150 amino acids, while the structure shows 101-161 amino acids.

Conflicting secondary structure elements between AlphaFold2 and NMR models

Using STRIDE, a secondary structure (SS) element is assigned to each residue of the AlphaFold2 model of a protein, and to each residue of the models in the NMR ensemble of the protein. When a residue has an equal assignment in all models (one AlphaFold2 model and one (or more) NMR models), we say that the residue has identical SS. When a residue has a different assigned SS in the AlphaFold2 model compared to its assigned SS in all the protein's NMR models, we say that the residue has a conflicting SS. Besides these residues with conflicting SS and identical SS, there is a third group of residues: a residue might have an AlphaFold2 assigned SS that is identical to the SS in some of the NMR models but conflicting in some of the other NMR models of the

protein.

There are 746 unique proteins with 746 AlphaFold2 models and 746 NMR ensembles (totaling 14,069 NMR models), corresponding to 14,069 AlphaFold2-NMR pairs (see main text). Out of the 74,879 unique residues of these proteins that are present in the AlphaFold2 sequence and the NMR models (overlapping), several residues (19,561) from one or more NMR models of the same ensemble exhibit indeed both conflicting and identical secondary structures. This variability arises because different NMR models within the same ensemble can show different secondary structures for the same residues. These residues are shown as the overlap between conflicting and identical secondary structures in Supplementary Fig. 6.24. The distribution of S_{RCI}^2 , RMSF, and pLDDT for residues with conflicting secondary structures (6,738 residues) is shown in Supplementary Fig. 6.25. The Pearson correlation coefficient between S_{RCI}^2 and RMSF for residues with conflicting secondary structures (SS) is -0.17 (p-value = 1.26×10^{-44} , $N = 6,258$ where N is the number of amino acids with S_{RCI}^2 available values). For S_{RCI}^2 and pLDDT, the Pearson correlation is 0.44 (p-value = 0.94×10^{-308} , $N = 6,258$), and it is -0.14 (p-value = 6.96×10^{-35} , $N = 6,738$) for RMSF and pLDDT.

We also examined the conflicting SS residues for each structure in 14,069 AlphaFold2-NMR pairs, identifying a total of 14,006 AlphaFold2-NMR pairs with conflicting SS residues. For these 14,006 pairs, we computed the difference in the Pearson correlation coefficients ($\rho_{k,m}^{\text{NMR}}$ and $\rho_{k,m}^{\text{AF2}}$, for detailed explanation see results section 3.5.2 in main) of AlphaFold2-NMR pairs (Eq. 6.1). The values $\Delta\rho_{k,m} > 0$ indicates that $\rho_{k,m}^{\text{NMR}}$ is stronger than $\rho_{k,m}^{\text{AF2}}$, while $\Delta\rho_{k,m} < 0$ indicates that $\rho_{k,m}^{\text{AF2}}$ is stronger than $\rho_{k,m}^{\text{NMR}}$. Out of 14,006 AlphaFold2-NMR pairs, 9,994 showed stronger $\rho_{k,m}^{\text{NMR}}$, and the remaining 4,012 pairs showed stronger $\rho_{k,m}^{\text{AF2}}$. The distribution of conflicting SS residues for both cases is shown in Supplementary Fig. 6.26. For AlphaFold2 models where correlation between S_{RCI}^2 vs RMSF is stronger than NMR models, the percentage of conflicting SS residues range from 0.86% to 80.48%, with an average of $19.46 \pm 10.18\%$ conflicting SS residues across the overlapping sequences of AlphaFold2 and NMR models. In comparison, for NMR models, the range is from 1.01% to 88.00% with an average of $19.07 \pm 9.91\%$ conflicting SS residues.

$$\Delta\rho_{k,m} = \rho_{k,m}^{\text{AF2}} - \rho_{k,m}^{\text{NMR}} \quad (6.1)$$

Supplementary Fig. 6.24: **Total conflicting secondary structure residues.** The Venn diagram representing total number of unique residues for 14,069 AlphaFold2-NMR pairs with conflicting secondary structure residues and identical secondary structure residues.

Supplementary Fig. 6.25: **Conflicting secondary structure residues.** A) S^2_{RCI} vs pLDDT, B) S^2_{RCI} vs RMSF, and C) pLDDT vs RMSF of 6,738 residues with conflicting secondary structures between AlphaFold2-NMR pairs are shown. The A, B, and C are visualized with a Gaussian kernel estimator between their corresponding x-axis and y-axis variables.

Supplementary Fig. 6.26: **Distribution of conflicting SS residues in AlphaFold2-NMR pairs.** The distribution of conflicting SS residues is shown as percentage on x-axis for A) AlphaFold2 models where the correlation between S_{RCI}^2 vs RMSF is stronger than NMR models, and B) NMR models where the correlation between S_{RCI}^2 vs RMSF is stronger than AlphaFold2 models.

Supplementary Table 6.9: **Examples of proteins with Pearson correlation coefficients between S_{RC1}^2 vs RMSF.** The Pearson correlation coefficients of specific proteins with their unique UniProt ID are reported for their respective AlphaFold2 and NMR models, including the number of conflicting residues occurring between the overlapping sequence of between the AlphaFold2 and NMR models, and total number of residues in the non-truncated and truncated AlphaFold2 models. For the NMR models, an example of only one structure from the NMR ensemble is provided.

UniProt ID	Correlation coefficient (AF2)	Correlation coefficient (NMR)	# conflicting residues	Total overlapping residues	Conflicting residues (%)	Total # residues (non-truncated)	Total # residues (non-truncated)
C3VPR6	-0.75	-0.73	13.85	87	15.92	1915	1898
O43157	-0.60	-0.46	21.95	112	19.60	2135	2122
O60885	-0.65	-0.78	15.00	83	18.07	1362	1315
P00519	-0.89	-0.83	26.50	97	27.32	1130	1081
P16157	-0.64	-0.66	15.70	104	15.10	1881	1817
P26039	-0.82	-0.78	12.00	132	9.09	2541	2523
P35670	-0.81	-0.86	29.00	161	18.01	1465	1352
P36006	-0.84	-0.87	13.05	69	18.91	1272	1230
P38398	-0.58	-0.57	29.07	104	27.95	1863	1851
P59046	-0.79	-0.68	28.00	93	30.11	1061	1056
Q04656	-0.73	-0.68	57.15	181	31.57	1500	1436
Q53F7	-0.52	-0.76	19.15	79	24.24	1128	1041
Q63HR2	-0.54	-0.79	23.55	114	20.66	1409	1375
Q92625	-0.58	-0.76	26.00	80	32.50	1134	1069
Q9P212	-0.73	-0.86	25.95	101	25.69	2302	1881